

SCREENING OF PHYTOCHEMICAL STUDIES, ANTIOXIDANT ACTIVITY, FTIR ANALYSIS AND ANTIBACTERIAL ASSAY OF METHANOLIC EXTRACT OF *Trapa bispinosa* Roxb.

Koba Doke^{1*}, Topi Karga², N. Rabita³, Debasish Dikshit⁴ and A. Venkatesan⁵

^{1*}*M.Sc. Botany, Department of Botany, Annamalai University*

²*Ph.D research scholar, Department of Botany, Annamalai University*

³*Ph.D research scholar, Department of Botany, Annamalai University*

⁴*Ph.D research scholar, Department of Botany, Annamalai University*

⁵*Associate Professor, Department of Botany, Annamalai University*

*Correspondence author**

M.Sc. Botany, Department of Botany, Annamalai University

ABSTRACT

Phytochemicals are naturally occurring compounds in plants with various health benefits, including antioxidant properties that protect against oxidative stress linked to aging and diseases. This study aimed to identify and quantify phytochemicals in a methanolic whole plant extract and evaluate its antioxidant activity using FRAP and DPPH assays. Qualitative analysis detected saponins, alkaloids, phenols, steroids, and flavonoids, indicating diverse biological activities. Quantitative analysis revealed total phenol content of 0.45 mg/g (gallic acid equivalents) and total flavonoid content of 0.74 mg/g (quercetin equivalents), suggesting significant health benefits. The extract showed notable antioxidant activity in the DPPH assay, with a maximum radical scavenging activity (%RSA) of 90.37 ± 0.88 at 200 $\mu\text{g/ml}$, while ascorbic acid had an %RSA of 124.39 ± 0.84 . The IC₅₀ values were 186.33 ± 1.2 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ for the extract and 111.58 ± 0.89 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ for ascorbic acid. The methanolic whole plant extract contains various phytochemicals with potential health benefits and exhibits significant antioxidant activity, effectively scavenging DPPH radicals. FTIR analysis also showed the presence of different types of compounds with different frequency and absorption intensity. Antibacterial assay was done using bacteria i.e., *E. faecalis* (gram +ve) and *E. coli* (gram -ve). It showed highest zone of inhibition in T₃ (18.6 ± 0.12 and 12.6 ± 2.33 respectively) at 250 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ with standard using ciprofloxacin and ampicillin.

Keywords – *Trapa bispinosa*, FRAP, DPPH, FTIR, Antibacterial activity

INTRODUCTION

Trapa bispinosa classified as an aquatic floating herb within the Trapaceae family, is prevalent in lakes and ponds across Africa and Asia and is often cultivated for its edible fruit. Both the entire herb and its fruit have been extensively documented in traditional medicine, demonstrating efficacy against various ailments. Comprehensive studies have highlighted the herb's hepatoprotective, antimicrobial, antibacterial, antitumor, antioxidant and free radical scavenging properties. Traditional medicine, rooted in ancient practices, constitutes a repository of knowledge, skills, and methodologies informed by diverse cultural perspectives. Despite occasional ambiguities, traditional medicine plays a crucial role in health preservation. It represents a synthesis of accumulated experiences from generations of physicians practicing indigenous medical systems. The terms alternative, complementary, non-conventional and indigenous medicine are often used interchangeably, particularly in countries where they contrast with conventional medicine. India, one of the 12 mega biodiversity centers, hosts an unparalleled plant diversity with 45,000 species across 16 agro-climatic regions, 10 vegetative zones, and 15 biotic regions. This rich floral diversity positions India as a prominent practitioner of traditional medicines such as Ayurveda, Unani, Siddha, and Homeopathy. Traditional medicinal formulations encompass therapeutic plants, minerals, and organic substances. Furthermore, many therapeutic drugs in conventional medicine trace their origins to plants, underscoring the indirect dependence on traditional medicine (Singh *et al.*, 2016; Kinoshita *et al.*, 2020; Yang *et al.*, 2020).

Research indicates that *Trapa bispinosa* is rich in bioactive compounds distributed across various plant parts. Qualitative analyses reveal the presence of carbohydrates, reducing sugar, starch, protein and flavonoids in *Trapa bispinosa* fruits, with methanol extracts exhibiting antibacterial and immunomodulatory activities (Pandey, 2019). Leaves of *Trapa bispinosa* contain carbohydrates, phenols, saponins, carboxylic acid, and fixed oils and fats, showcasing antioxidant and anti-proliferative activities (Agarwal and Methwani, 2019; Xia *et al.*, 2017). The dried fruit shell is commonly utilized in tea and herbal medicines in India and Japan (Wang *et al.*, 2022). Phytochemical screening of pericarp extract has identified various secondary metabolites, with the pericarp demonstrating antioxidant, antibacterial and antimicrobial properties without adverse effects (Stoicescu *et al.*, 2012; Verma *et al.*, 2013).

The aim of this study is followed by the objectives to qualitative analysis of the bioactive components present in the crude extract and to determine the total phenolic content (TPC) and total flavonoid content (TFC) of *Trapa bispinosa*. To check the antioxidant activity of crude plant extract using different methods viz., DPPH and FRAP. And also, studies on antibacterial activity against both *E. faecalis* and *E. coli*.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

PLANT SOURCE

Trapa bispinosa whole plant was collected from Laphupat tera, Bishnupur district, Manipur, India on 28-03-2023 and used for the present investigation. The taxonomic authenticity of the above plant was identified by Dr. D. Kumarasamy, renowned taxonomist, Annamalai University. The whole plants were surface sterilized with 1% mercuric chloride and thoroughly washed with plenty of distilled water. The plant material was dried under shade with occasional shifting. Later, the dried plant materials were chopped into small piece and stored in an airtight container. Solvent methanol was used in extraction procedure.

Identification of secondary metabolites

Qualitative phytochemical analysis

The crude plant extracts of *Trapa bispinosa* in methanol were qualitatively analyzed for the identification of secondary metabolites viz., alkaloids, flavonoids, glycosides, phenols, saponins, steroids, terpenoids, anthraquinone, phlobatannin and tannins by using standard protocols (Nagababu, 2012; Nurdiani, *et al.*, 2012).

Quantitative phytochemical analysis

(i) Estimation of Total Phenol content (TPC): This method was followed according to Slinkard and Singleton (1977).

Determination of total phenolics by spectrophotometric method: The amount of total phenolics in extracts was determined according to the Folin-Ciocalteu procedure. A different volume of working standard gallic acid solutions was introduced into test tubes and for test instead of gallic acid, crude plant extracts was used. Add 5ml of Folin-Ciocalteu reagent allow standing for 5min in dark. Then add 4ml of sodium carbonate (7.5%) were added and kept in dark for 90min at 23°C. The tubes were mixed and allowed to stand for 1min. Absorption at 765 nm was measured. The total phenolic content was expressed as gallic acid equivalents (GAE) in

micrograms per gram tissue as calculated from standard gallic acid graph. For standard different concentrations of working standard gallic acid 20,40,60,80 and 100µg/ml at a concentrations range 50-200µg/ml, in a series of test tubes a blank was prepared separately with 1ml of distilled water and for test 1ml crude extract at 100µg/ml; 5ml of Folin-Ciocalteu reagent and 4ml of sodium carbonate was added and incubated at 23°C for 90min. The tubes were mixed and allowed to stand for 1min. The color developed was measured the absorption at 765 nm was measured.

$$\text{Total phenol content(TPC)} = \frac{CV}{M} \text{ mg/gm}$$

C = Concentration of gallic acid from calibration curve

V= Volume of extract in ml

M=Weight of plant extracts in gm.

(ii) Estimation of Total Flavonoid Content (TFC)

Aluminum chloride colorimetric method was used for total phenols determined by Park *et al.*, (2008) and Marinova *et al.*, (2007).

Estimation of total flavonoid content: In a 10ml test tube, 1ml of crude plant extract at a concentration of 100µg/ml for test, and for standard different volumes of 30% methanolic quercetin 0.2, 0.4, 0.6, 0.8 and 1ml at a concentrations range 20-100µg/ml. To this add 0.3ml of NaNO₂ (0.5M) and 0.3ml of AlCl₃ (0.3M) were mixed. After 5min, 2ml of NaOH (1M) was added and finally make up by 10ml H₂O. The solution was mixed well and the absorbance was measured against the reagent blank at 506nm. The standard curve for total flavonoids was made using quercetin standard solution(0.1mg/ml) under the same procedure as earlier described. The total flavonoids were expressed as mg of quercetin equivalents per g of dried fraction.

$$\text{Total flavonoid content} = \frac{R \times D \cdot F \times V}{W} \times 100$$

R = Results obtained from standard curve

D.F = Dilution factor

V = Volume of stock solution

100= 100µg of dried extract

W=Weight of plant used in gm.

Non enzymatic antioxidant assays

(i) DPPH radical Scavenging Activity: This method was followed according to Alam *et al.* (2013).

The plant extract 0.1ml was dissolved in respective solvent acetone (0.9ml) and 2 ml of DPPH solution (0.5 mM) was added after 30 min, the absorbance was measured at 517 nm. Lower absorbance of the reaction mixture indicates higher free radical scavenging activity. The antioxidant activity of the extract was expressed as IC₅₀, which was defined as the concentration (µg/ml) of extract that inhibits the formation of DPPH radicals by 50%. Each study corresponded to three experiments and performed in duplicate. The free-radical scavenging activity of the various fractions of BHT was measured with the stable radical diphenylpicrylhydrazyl (DPPH) in terms of hydrogen donating or radical-scavenging activity.

The percentage of the DPPH radical scavenging was calculated using the equation as given below:

$$\% \text{ inhibition} = (\text{Absorbance of control} - \text{Absorbance of test} / \text{Absorbance of control}) \times 100$$

(ii) FRAP Assay (Ferric reduced antioxidant potential): This method was followed according to Benzie and Strain method (1996).

Determination of FRAP method:

To 3ml of prepared FRAP reagent is mixed with different volumes of standard ascorbic acid 50,100,150 and 200µl at a concentration range 50-200µg/ml and note the absorbance at 593 nm after a 30 min incubation at 37°C FRAP values can be obtained by comparing the absorption change in the test mixture with those obtained from increasing concentration of ascorbic acid equivalents moles/ml or FRAP units. The antioxidant activity of the extract was expressed as IC₅₀, which was defined as the concentration (µg/ml) of extract that inhibits the formation of DPPH radicals by 50%.Ascorbic acid was used as positive controls.

FTIR analysis

Using a Fourier transform infrared spectrophotometer (FTIR), the functional groups present in the plant extract components are detected. The annotated spectrum provides the wavelength of absorbed light, which indicates the chemical bond. On an Agilent FTIR spectrometer was then used to analyze from the whole plant extract of the *Trapa bispinosa*.

Antibacterial assay

A positive control (T₄), negative control (T₀), 62.5µg/ml (T₁), 125µg/ml (T₂) and 250µg/ml (T₃), and an extract solution were all prepared. Ceftriaxone, the positive control, had a concentration of 30 g/ml, and DMSO, the negative control, was chosen. Pathogenic bacteria (*E. faecalis* and *E. coli*) were grown in a subculture on nutrient agar. Using the agar well diffusion method, pathogenic microorganisms were tested for inhibitory effects. In Muller-Hinton agar plates, the agar well diffusion technique was performed. A cotton swab was used to apply a standardized bacterial suspension plate, and a standard well borer was used to create well that were 6 mm in diameter. 50µl of each extract were added to the well containing the drugs DMSO which served as the corresponding negative drugs where ampicillin and ciprofloxacin used as standard or positive control for both *E. faecalis* and *E. coli*. For 24 hours, these inoculated plates were incubated at 37⁰C. The inhibitory zone (measured in mm) was recorded in triplicate of each trial.

Statistical analysis

The triplicates of data obtained from the experimental study were subjected to statistical analysis by SPSS DMRT (Duncan's Multiple Range Test) and Graph pad prism version 8. Mean and standard deviation were calculated.

RESULTS

Preliminary phytochemical analysis

Qualitative phytochemical analysis

Appropriate phytochemical tests were employed to investigate the phytochemical constituents present in the crude extract of *Trapa bispinosa* Roxb. The preliminary phytochemical analysis of ten different secondary metabolites was performed in methanol extracts of *Trapa bispinosa*. Nine tests conferred positive results and remaining eight gave

negative result. The plant species showed significant indication about the presence of various bioactive secondary metabolites *viz.*, saponin, alkaloid, phenol, steroids and flavonoids (**Table 1**).

Table1. Preliminary qualitative phytochemical analysis of *Trapa bispinosa*

Secondary metabolites	Tests Performed	Observation	Result
Saponin	Foam test	Foam persists more than 10 minutes	+++
	Froth test	Persistent foam	++
Tannin	1% HCl test	No formation of red precipitate	-
Alkaloid	Mayer's test	Buff colored precipitate appears	+
	Wagner's test	Formation of red precipitate appears	++
Phenol	Ellagic test	Chocolate brown color appears	+
Phlobatannin	1% HCl test	No formation of red precipitate	-
Steroids	Salkowski's test	No formation of reddish-brown color	-
	Lieberman-Burchard's test	Color development from violet to blue	+
		No appearance of reddish-brown ring	-
Keller-Killiani test			
Terpenoids	Glacial acetic test	No pink to violet color formation	-
Glycosides	Conc. H ₂ SO ₄ test	No formation of red color	-
	Keller-Killiani test	No formation of reddish-brown ring	-
Anthraquinone	Borntrager's test	No appearance of pink, red or violet color	-
Flavonoids	1% ammonia test	Appearance of yellow color	+
	Shinoda test	Appearance of red color	+
	Lead-acetate test	Appearance of buff color	++

+++Highly present; ++ Moderately present; + Lightly present; - Absent

Quantitative phytochemical analysis

Total Phenolic Content

The plant phenolics constituent is one of the major groups of the compounds acting as primary antioxidants or free radical scavengers. The antioxidant activity of the phenolic compounds is mainly due to their redox properties, which can play an important role in absorbing and neutralizing free radicals, quenching singlet and triplet oxygen or decomposing peroxides. The total phenolics content in the methanolic plant extracts was determined using the

Folin-Ciocalteu assay. The content of phenolics in the extract of *Trapa bispinosa* was **0.45mg/g GAE. (Fig 1).**

Fig. 1. Graph Showing Standard Curve for Total Phenolic Content (Gallic Acid)

Total Flavonoid Content

Flavonoids protect cells against the damaging effects of reactive oxygen species, such as singlet oxygen, superoxide, peroxy radicals, hydroxyl radicals, and peroxynitrite. Epidemiological studies have shown that flavonoid intake is inversely related to mortality from coronary heart disease and the incidence of heart attacks. Flavonoid content was calculated from the regression equation of the calibration curve and is expressed as Quercetin equivalents (QE). The flavonoid content was **0.74 mg/g QE** in *Trapa bispinosa* and the result is presented in Fig 2.

Fig.2. Graph Showing Standard Curve for Total Flavonoid Content (Quercetin)

Antioxidant activity of methanolic crude extract of *Trapa bispinosa*.

DPPH (2,2-diphenyl-1-picrylhydrazyl) Radical Scavenging Activity

The DPPH Assay showed that the highest %RSA in methanolic whole plant extract 90.37 ± 0.88 with standard 124.39 ± 0.84 at $200 \mu\text{g/ml}$. The IC₅₀ value at whole plant ascorbic acid at $50\text{-}200 \mu\text{g/ml}$ was showed 186.33 ± 1.2 and 111.58 ± 0.89 respectively shown in **Fig 3**.

The results of the DPPH assay indicate that the methanolic whole plant extract exhibited a high percentage of Radical Scavenging Activity (%RSA) at $200 \mu\text{g/ml}$, with a value of $90.37\% \pm 0.88$. This suggests that the extract has strong antioxidant properties, as it was able to effectively scavenge free radicals.

Comparatively, the standard ascorbic acid showed a higher %RSA at $124.39\% \pm 0.84$, indicating that it is a more potent antioxidant than the plant extract at the same concentration. The IC₅₀ values provide further insights into the antioxidant activity. The IC₅₀ value represents the concentration at which the extract or standard is able to scavenge 50% of the free radicals. A lower IC₅₀ value indicates a higher antioxidant activity.

In this case, the IC₅₀ value of the whole plant extract with ascorbic acid at 50-200 µg/ml was 186.33 ± 1.2 and 111.58 ± 0.89 , respectively. This indicates that the ascorbic acid has a lower IC₅₀ value compared to the plant extract, suggesting that it is more effective at scavenging free radicals and therefore has stronger antioxidant activity in this assay.

Overall, these results suggest that the methanolic whole plant extract has significant antioxidant activity, although not as potent as the standard ascorbic acid. This could be valuable information for further studies on the potential health benefits of this plant extract.

Fig. 3. Graph shows the antioxidant activity of whole plant methanolic extract of *Trapa bispinosa* using DPPH assay by comparing with ascorbic acid (standard).

FRAP Assay (Ferric Reduced Antioxidant Potential)

The results of the Ferric Reducing Power Assay indicate the antioxidant activity of the methanolic whole plant extract and standard ascorbic acid at different concentrations (50, 100, 150, and 200 µg/ml). The methanolic whole plant extract showed %RSA values of $30.49\% \pm 0.98$ at 50 µg/ml, increasing to $65.35\% \pm 1.21$ at 200 µg/ml. In comparison, ascorbic acid exhibited %RSA values of $40.38\% \pm 1.11$ at 50 µg/ml, increasing to $124.39\% \pm 0.89$ at 200 µg/ml (Fig 4). These results suggest that both the extract and ascorbic acid exhibit increasing reducing power with higher concentrations, with ascorbic acid generally showing higher reducing power than the plant extract across all concentrations. The IC₅₀ value represents the concentration at which the extract or standard is able to reduce 50% of the ferric ions. Lower IC₅₀ values indicate higher reducing power. The IC₅₀ value of the methanolic whole plant extract with ascorbic acid at 50-

200 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ was 156.35 ± 1.09 and 111.58 ± 0.89 , respectively. This suggests that ascorbic acid has a lower IC_{50} value compared to the plant extract, indicating higher reducing power and stronger antioxidant activity in this assay.

Fig. 4. Graph shows the antioxidant activity of whole plant methanolic extract of *Trapa bispinosa* Roxb. using FRAP assay by comparing with ascorbic acid (standard).

FT-IR spectroscopic analysis of methanolic whole plant extracts of *Trapa bispinosa* Roxb.

Fig 5 showed the FTIR analysis of methanolic whole plant extract of *Trapa bispinosa* Roxb showed 6 frequencies and different types of compounds like alcohol, aromatic compounds, imine, carboxylic acid and amine with different absorption intensity (Table 2).

Fig. 5. FTIR spectrum shows various frequencies of methanolic whole plant extracts of *Trapa bispinosa* Roxb.

Table 2. Table represents the frequencies, vibration type and type of compounds

Sl. No.	Frequency (Cm ⁻¹)	Absorption Intensity	Vibration type	Band Assignment	Type of Compounds
1.	3362.1	Strong, Broad	Stretching	O-H	Alcohol
2.	2098.5	Weak	Bending	C-H	Aromatic compound
3.	1636.3	Medium	Stretching	C=N	Imine / Oxime
4.	1423.8	Medium	Bending	O-H	Carboxylic acid
5.	1144.3	Medium	Stretching	C-N	Amine
6.	1051.1	Medium	Stretching	C-N	Amine

Antibacterial assay

Methanolic crude extract of whole plant of *Trapa bispinosa* showed antibacterial activity against both gram +ve and gram -ve bacteria i.e., *E. faecalis* and *E.coli* respectively. And it showed inhibition zone highest in gram +ve than that of gram -ve bacteria. *E. faecalis* (gram +ve) showed highest zone of inhibition in T₃(18.6 ± 0.12 mm) at concentration 250 µg/ml with standard T₄19.6 ± 0.23 mm whereas, *E.coli* (gram -ve) showed highest zone of inhibition T₃ (12.6 ± 2.33) at concentration 250 µg/ml. Ciprofloxacin and ampicillin was used as standard or positive control for gram -ve and gram +ve respectively. DMSO was used as negative control.

Table 3. Table represents Zone of inhibition of two bacterial strains.

Pathogenic bacteria	Experimental units	Clear zone (mm) \pm standard deviation
<i>E.faecalis</i>	T ₁	13.6 \pm 0.024
	T ₂	15.6 \pm 0.75
	T ₃	18.6 \pm 0.12
	T ₄	19.6 \pm 0.23
	T ₀	0 \pm 0.00
<i>E.coli</i>	T ₁	7.6 \pm 0.57
	T ₂	9.6 \pm 0.24
	T ₃	12.6 \pm 2.33
	T ₄	14.2 \pm 0.24
	T ₀	0 \pm 0.00

DISCUSSION

The extracts of *Trapa bispinosa* yielded approximately 30% and are rich in various classes of phytochemicals, including alkaloids, tannins, flavonoids, glycosides, and steroids (Table 1). These phytoconstituents exert diverse physiological effects depending on their composition (Singh et al., 2016). Table 1 indicates that the extract tested positive for alkaloids, steroids, phenols, saponins, and flavonoids, while it tested negative for tannins, phlobatannins, terpenoids, glycosides, and anthraquinones. Previous studies have identified alkaloids and gum in the plant extract (Karmarkar et al., 2011), and another study found high quantities of saponin alkaloids in *T. bispinosa* (Mann et al., 2012).

The methanolic extracts of *Trapa bispinosa* leaves exhibited significant antioxidant activity. The observed DPPH scavenging activity in the methanolic leaf extracts may contribute to the development of potent natural antioxidants. Additionally, the plant extract demonstrated a strong cytotoxic effect (Tania et al., 2014).

Trapa bispinosa contains phytochemicals such as malic acid, oxalic acid, gallic acid, betulic acid, quercetin, myricetin, and myricitin. Myricetin is a strong antioxidant, while quercetin has a protective effect in neurological disorders. Due to their antioxidant-rich phytochemical composition, these plants have significant therapeutic potential against various

diseases, including infectious diseases of bacterial, fungal, and viral nature, lifestyle diseases such as diabetes and hypertension, neurological diseases like epilepsy and dementia, neurodegenerative diseases like Alzheimer's and Parkinson's, as well as various forms of cancer (Choi and Choi, 2010).

The present investigation supports *Trapa bispinosa* as a promising source of natural antioxidants. Antioxidant properties varied significantly between the two methods used, depending on the phytoconstituents' content and composition. Among these methods, FRAP demonstrated very strong antioxidant properties. Although DPPH showed less antioxidant activity in an inverse dose-dependent manner compared to FRAP in this study, it does not diminish the plant's therapeutic value due to the presence of flavonoids. These results are consistent with previous studies (Singh *et al.*, 2016; Javed *et al.*, 2016; Bokhari *et al.*, 2020).

The antibacterial effects of *Trapa bispinosa* are attributed to the presence of bioactive components, including flavonoids, tannins, saponins, and polyphenols (Prakash and Gupta, 2013). Research has demonstrated that *Trapa bispinosa* extracts can stop the growth of a number of bacteria, such as *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Escherichia coli*, and *Staphylococcus aureus* (Jadhav *et al.*, 2009). According to Devi and Rajendran (2013), the antibacterial activity is thought to result from the rupture of bacterial cell walls and the suppression of protein synthesis. *Trapa bispinosa* has been studied in a variety of solvents, including ethanol, methanol, and aqueous extracts; ethanol extracts often demonstrated the strongest antibacterial activity (Bisht and Bhandari, 2016). *Trapa bispinosa* has the potential to be a natural antibacterial agent because it is used in traditional medicine to treat infections. Additional research and clinical trials are needed to confirm its efficacy and safety (Patel, 2012).

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